

ELIXIR
Compute Platform
2024-26
Work Plan

Abstract

The ELIXIR Compute Platform ensures that European cloud, compute, storage and access services fulfil the requirements and are available for the life-science research community. European regulation on health data processing is evolving, computing capacity in national clouds is increasing and international standards are improving interoperability between the compute environments. Such capabilities are also increasingly important to service the growing volumes of biodiversity, food security and pathogen data which comprise complex data types and must be linked to climate data resources. Also, supercomputer investments - especially EuroHPC - provide completely new kinds of computing capacities for researchers across these domains.

All this shapes the landscape of European compute resources. Especially, computing on sensitive data near the data resources is becoming obligatory but the same is true for non-sensitive data e.g. plant phenotyping data and associated imaging data. In 2024-26, the Platform will build technological capability to enable compute in new European-wide federated and multi-cloud settings by building on existing development and utilising previous work, especially Life Science Login. Beyond this, the platform actively seeks sustainable ways to operate the developed services for European researchers.

The Platform will **deliver the services to support federated data management and analytics in life science** through 4 complementary WPs:

- **WP2** - Advanced Service Access Control
- **WP3** - Protected Access to Sensitive Data for Analysis
- **WP4** - Multi Cloud Infrastructure Deployment
- **WP5** - Sustainability, Accounting and Provenance for Federated Analytics

About this document

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1. Objectives and relation to the Scientific Programme

The ELIXIR Compute Platform serves as an expert group for computation of life sciences data in ELIXIR, focusing on areas such as Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), Cloud Computing, Hybrid Cloud solutions, and adherence to GA4GH compute standards, exemplified by projects like ELIXIR::GA4GH Cloud and AAI. Its success lies in having fostered a vibrant community engaged in diverse aspects of computational needs required for the life sciences.

The Compute Platform leverages ELIXIR's extensive network, comprising Platforms, Communities, and Focus Groups. This network facilitates collaborative discussions, connects compute and High Performance Computing service providers and users, and resources across Nodes, and harnesses technological advancements for transformative progress. As computational demands and challenges evolve, the Compute Platform remains committed to advancing computational life sciences and addressing the needs of European researchers and users.

For 2024-2026 the Compute Platform thematic priorities are Advanced Service Access Control, Protected Access to Sensitive Data for Analysis, Multi-Cloud Infrastructure Deployment, and Sustainability, Accounting, and Provenance for Federated Analytics. Within this realm of expertise, the Compute Platform serves as a driving force for computational advancements in life sciences within the ELIXIR consortium in alignment with the ELIXIR Strategic Programme 2024-2028.

Thematic areas

Advanced Service Access Control

- Science Priority (S₃): By enhancing authentication and authorization mechanisms, this work package directly enables scientists to securely access and analyse life science data across all science priorities, ensuring compliance with data privacy regulations and promoting data sharing. This work package will have a particular focus in developing solutions for barriers to sensitive data access such as that of human genomics.
- Technology Priority (T₃): The focus on federated service delivery of LS-AAI aligns with the technology priority of delivering services to support federated data management and analytics, creating a seamless experience for users across the ELIXIR Nodes.

Protected Access to Sensitive Data for Analysis

- Science Priority (S₃): Enabling secure access and analysis of sensitive data directly supports the Human Data science priority by facilitating protected research access for human data translational research.
- Technology Priority (T₂, T₃): The work package aligns with exploring service solutions for reproducible analytics and federated service delivery ensuring secure and regulated access to sensitive data while promoting data sharing and analysis.

Multi Cloud Infrastructure Deployment

- Science Priority (S₃): Developing a multi-cloud infrastructure directly supports scientists' access to computational resources for analysing cellular, molecular, biodiversity, and translational data, enhancing research capabilities across all science priorities. In particular the science priority of Human Data will be met through the development of ELIXIR's work on GA4GH standards to facilitate the envisioned multi cloud reality.

- Technology Priority (T2, T3): Developing a federated hybrid- and multicloud-ready platform aligns with ELIXIR's technology priority of delivering services for federated data management and analytics, supporting reproducible analytics, and enhancing the possibility of research data management.

Sustainability, Accounting and Provenance for Federated Analytics

- Science Priority (S3): Addressing sustainability, accounting, and provenance directly benefits scientists' research by ensuring transparent resource reporting and reproducibility of analytics, which is a priority for Human Data translational research.
- Technology Priority (T2, T3): Tracking provenance aligns with reproducible analytics and infrastructure, while resource reporting and accounting support research data management and data sharing.

In conclusion, this focused effort further solidifies the Compute Platform's role as an essential expert group within ELIXIR, driving computational excellence, capacity and fostering collaboration across diverse domains of life sciences research.

2. Partnership

Contributors to the work programme are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Overview of involved institutions.

Node	Institution	Abbreviation
Lead Institutions		
CZ	Masaryk University	CZ-MUNI
DE	Berlin Institute of Health at Charité	DE-BIH/Charite
FI	CSC	FI-CSC
Member Institutions		
BE	VIB	BE-VIB
CH	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB)	CH-SIB
CZ	CESNET	CZ-CESNET
DE	Forschungszentrum Jülich	DE-FZJU
DE	German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ)	DE-DKFZ
DE	Giessen University	DE-Giessen
EE	University of Tartu	EE-UTARTU
ELIXIR	ELIXIR Hub	ELIXIR-HUB
EMBL	European Bioinformatics Institute	EMBL-EBI
FR	Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS)	FR-CNRS
FR	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (France)	FR-INRAE
GR	Athena Research and Innovation Centre (ARC)	GR-ATHENA
IT	The National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN) / Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)	IT-INFN
LU	PNED G.I.E.	LU-LNDS
LU	University Luxembourg	LU-UNILU
NL	Erasmus Medical Center	NL-Erasmus
NL	Health RI (Stichting)	NL-Health-RI
NL	SURF	NL-SURF

UK	The University of Manchester	UK-UNIMAN
International Partners		
AU	Australian BioCommons	AU-AUS Biocommons

3. Work Package descriptions

Work Package 1 - Platform Management and Coordination

WP 1	Lead Partner: FI-CSC, CZ-MUNI, DE-BIH/Charite	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
CZ-MUNI - Ludek Matyska (lead)		
DE-BIH - Harald Wagener (lead)		
FI-CSC - Juha Törnroos (lead)		
ELIXIR-HUB - Jonathan Tedds (Coordinator), Gavin Farrell (Technical Officer)		
<p>Objectives</p> <p>The purpose of this work package is to provide the overall project management and coordination of the activities of ELIXIR Compute Platform. This work package ensures that Platform work progresses as planned.</p> <p>The work package will also ensure that the platform work plan is aligned with ELIXIR’s strategic vision and key EC funded projects where ELIXIR leads or participates including GDI, ENTRUST, STEERS and EVERSE which are relevant for the overall development of European research infrastructures, data spaces and regulation. The work package facilitates active dialog with life-science research communities in order to understand the real needs of researchers. This is done especially by collaborating with ELIXIR Communities that represent researchers’ use cases.</p> <p>Besides technology development, delivering impact on research requires that the technology can be sustained and provided for researchers. This work package seeks ways how the developed technology can be sustained as part of operational services. This can be done both by integrating technology into existing services and by establishing new services when applicable.</p> <p>The landscape of European research infrastructures, data spaces and related initiatives, such as EOSC, EuroHPC and GAIA-X, are evolving and the work package is actively participating in this development. Establishing services in cross-infrastructure fashion and providing them in wider collaboration is seen as a favourable option. Especially partnering with other research infrastructures and providing services as part of EOSC service offering supports the objective of long term service sustainability. Also, the work package ensures that the platform activities are well connected and communicated to the research community.</p> <p>The work package will also bridge the platform activities to GA4GH and participate in the steering of GA4GH by utilising the ELIXIR and GA4GH strategic partnership.</p>		
<p>Description of Work</p> <p>Activity 1 Project management and coordination (<i>leads: Ludek Matyska/CZ-MUNI, Harald Wagener/DE-BIH/Charite, Juha Törnroos/FI-CSC</i>)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up and facilitate regular Platform wide meetings, both online and face-to-face 		

- Provide proper communication channels for the work
- Monitor and report the progress

Activity 2 Sustainability and dissemination (leads: Ludek Matyska/CZ-MUNI, Harald Wagener/DE-BIH/Charite, Juha Törnroos/FI-CSC)

- Ensure sufficient sustainability planning for platform development activities
- Ensure bi-directional communication about the Platform activities towards research communities, especially through ELIXIR Communities, ELIXIR Training Platform and utilising existing communications channels such as ELIXIR webinars
- Knowledge sharing with other ELIXIR platforms and participation in joint-platform activities
- Represent platform in the ELIXIR::GA4GH strategic partnership
- Dissemination for Compute Platform

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D1.1	Annual Report 2023	CZ-MUNI	M06
D1.2	Annual Report 2024	DE-BIH/Charite	M18
D1.3	Annual Report 2025	FI-CSC	M30
D1.4	2 Compute Platform articles submitted	CZ-MUNI	M30
D1.5	Alignment to prospective ELIXIR Cross Platform dissemination articles	DE-BIH	M30
D1.6	Preparation, writing and delivery of 2027-2028 Platform Plan	FI-CSC	M30
D1.7	End Report	CZ-MUNI	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M1.1	Platform F2F Event - Year 1	CZ-MUNI	M12
M1.2	Platform F2F Event - Year 2	DE-BIH	M24
M1.3	Platform F2F Event - Year 3	FI-CSC	M36

Work Package 2 - Advanced Service Access Control

WP 2	Lead Partner: CZ-MUNI, FI-CSC	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
CZ-MUNI - Dominik F. Bucik (lead)		
FI-CSC - Aino-Riikka Corell (lead)		
FI-CSC - Janne Lauros (member)		
CH-SIB - Alexander Kanitz (member)		
CZ-MUNI - Jan Pavlíček (member)		
CZ-MUNI - Pavlína Špringerová (member)		
CZ-MUNI - Peter Bolha (member)		
CZ-MUNI - Slávek Licehammer (member)		
CZ-MUNI - Jana Broncova (member)		
GR-ATHENA - Thanasis Vergoulis (member)		
GR-ATHENA - Eleni Adamidi (member)		
LU-LNDS - Christophe Trefois (member)		
LU-UNILU - Venkata Satagopam (member)		
LU-UNILU - Sascha Herzinger (member)		
WP Key External Collaborations		
AU-AUS Biocommons - Steven Manos (member)		
<p>Objectives</p> <p>An increasing number of services are moving towards working with sensitive data. Such services need to perform authentication of the person working with data and enforce authorization rules with a high level of assurance. ELIXIR has built and operated the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) service for such tasks, which formed the basis for the joint effort to create a common Life Science AAI (LS AAI) in the EOSC-Life project. The idea of a common AAI service is the ability to provide unified authentication mechanisms, a central place to execute authorization decisions and provide the ability for the relying services to outsource such tasks on the operated infrastructure. For authentication purposes, ELIXIR AAI and LS AAI are relying on the eduGAIN interfederation to enable researchers access to the services using their home organisations. The service is now a mature production service with over 13,000 users who login per month and increasing adoption by other Research Infrastructures in the EOSC-Life Science Cluster including BBMRI-ERIC and Instruct-ERIC [https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8144216].</p> <p>In the next phase, the authentication needs to move towards improving the assurance of the authentication process by adopting various mechanisms providing additional security for user accounts. As for the</p>		

authorization part, ELIXIR has been piloting the GA4GH Passports and Visa standard, as well as defining its own mechanisms for enabling distributed authorization. In the following development, distributed authorization will focus more on effectively defining authorization rules in different contexts and places, efficiently collecting them and applying them in a broad spectrum of places. This will boost real world capabilities for LS-AAI usage in critical projects such as GDI, where it is to be implemented as the first line of user access and control for accessing and processing sensitive genomic data across participating 1M+G European member states. New solutions will be tested in an even broader cross domain context across the science clusters through the EOSC AAI common framework. Last but not least, identity governance will be another point of interest for this task.

Description of Work

Activity 1 Advanced authentication mechanisms (leads: Dominik F. Bucik/CZ-MUNI, Aino-Riikka Corell/FI-CSC, members: Jana Broncová (CZ), Christophe Trefois (LU), Venkata Satagopam (LU), Sascha Herzinger (LU), Janne Lauros (FI), Dominik F. Bučik (CZ))

The goal of this work package is to explore new areas of authentication mechanisms by extending the basis built in the previous work packages. This WP will concentrate on exploring new approaches to working with digital identity like Self-Sovereign Identity, e-wallets, and similar technologies and rising alternatives to the traditional Identity Federations approach, while it will also try to integrate these solutions as alternatives to the authentication mechanisms in place.

The federated approach will be iterated on to reach out to entities not participating in the eduGAIN federation, like commercial entities from the pharmaceutical industry, who are not able to join such a federation. Thus, a focus will be building standardised solutions and procedures for integrating with such entities. The aim is also to extend the security aspects of the authentication process by exploring Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) in the widely distributed EOSC AAI environment.

This WP will additionally try to explore the possibility of providing passwordless authentication as an accompanying authentication mechanism in a federated login environment. By shifting towards this authentication mechanism we expect to achieve a more streamlined authentication process and expect the federative authentication to move towards the support role in the area of identity vetting and backup authentication solutions.

From the perspective of managing the identity for authentication purposes, we want to investigate the ability to correctly de-provision identity data, especially in distributed environments and improve the identity governance aspects by defining strict lifecycle policies of the identity and relevant data which are conformant with auditing and accounting needs.

- Explore digital wallets, Self-Sovereign Identities and new trends of working with digital identity, while providing such solutions as an alternative to the existing Identity Federations approach.
- Pilot integration of passwordless login as one of the login alternatives in an environment based on federated authentication mechanisms.
- Elaborate on the security of the authentication process by improving the user experience and handling of the Multi-Factor Authentication in a largely distributed and federated environment.
- Define standardised solution for Identity Governance tasks in the area of AAI
- Introduce effective de-provisioning mechanisms of identity data in a largely distributed and multi-federated environment (EOSC AAI including).
- Propose universal procedures and mechanisms for integrating entities from non-academic areas as authentication providers in the AAI ecosystem in a scalable and manageable way (e.g. via an automated registry tool).

Activity 2 Authorization in distributed infrastructures (leads: Dominik Bucik (CZ), Sascha Herzinger (LU) , members: Jan Pavlíček (CZ), Christophe Trefois (LU), Venkata Satagopam (LU), Sascha Herzinger (LU), Thanasis Vergoulis (GR), Eleni Adamidi (GR) , Alexander Kanitz (CH), Stefan Negru (FI), Janne Lauros (FI), Nils Hoffmann (DE), Slavek Licehammer (CZ), Dominik F. Bučik (CZ))

The traditional role of the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructures lies in basic authorization execution and mostly in providing authorization data to the relying parties, which can then perform local authorization based on this data. In the years of operating ELIXIR AAI and participation in Life Science AAI, we have learned about a lot of use cases shared across various relying parties. This work package should focus on extracting as many repetitive authorization scenarios as possible and integrating them directly into the AAI environment, to remove the burden of designing and implementing such authorization scenarios from the relying parties, enabling them to focus more on the provided functionality. Iterating on this approach, the goal is to provide Relying Parties, organisations, or managers within the AAI with a framework, where they can define authorization rules in the AAI itself and AAI will evaluate the conditions defined at the time of performing other authorization tasks, resulting in a simple AUTHORISED/UNAUTHORISED information provided to the service with a possible reasoning why the decision has been carried out. Such an approach could be even escalated into environments similar to EOSC AAI to explore these possibilities in a multi-federated and multi-infrastructure environment with an emphasis on efficient definition, sharing, execution and communication of these rules and their results.

We are also expecting continuous work on the existing standards like entitlements or GA4GH Passports and Visas with the possibility of extending their applicability into areas outside of the genomics data, and extending authorization into finer granularity level, file in a data set or sections of the file. Last but not least, with the increased emphasis on compliance with policies like GDPR and the need to manage approvals of policies like AUP, Privacy Notice, and Terms of Use, this work package will explore possibilities to record such things and re-use these records as another authorization data inputs.

Key work to be carried out:

- Design a mechanism of defining and executing repetitive authorization scenarios performed on the side of Relying Parties in the AAI.
- Explore possibilities for simplifying the evaluation and communication of defined authorization conditions at the time of performing other authorization tasks, resulting in simple AUTHORISED/UNAUTHORISED information provided to the service with reasoning why the respective decision has been carried out.
- Escalate the proposed AAI-hosted authorization approach into environments similar to EOSC AAI to explore the usage of such concepts possibilities in a multi-federated and multi-infrastructure environment with an emphasis on efficient definition, sharing, execution and communication of these rules and their results.
- Explore the existing standards like entitlements or GA4GH Passports and Visas, with the intention to extend their applicability, e.g. extending GA4GH Passports and Visas standards into areas outside of the genomics data.
- Extend possibilities to record policies like GDPR and manage approvals of policies like AUP, Privacy Notice, and Terms of Use and re-use these records as other authorization data inputs.
- Evaluate the concept of establishing an AAI API gateway usable by RPs as an authorization service as another alternative to the standardised integration protocols used by Relying Parties.

Activity 3 User Experience, community engagement, training and outreach (leads: Pavlina Špringerová (CZ), Eleni Adamidi (GR), members: Pavlína Špringerová (CZ), Peter Bolha (CZ), Aino-Riikka Corell (FI), Ivar Janmaat (NL), Harald Wagener (DE), Jana Broncova (CZ), Dominik F. Bučík (CZ), key external collaborations: Steven Manos (AU))

One of the main two ideas of Authentication and Authorization Infrastructures is to provide users accessing integrated services via a unified familiar process and to enable performing authorization for the whole infrastructure in a single place. Looking at the regular user process, the service access workflow might get fairly complicated, especially in the federated model, where users use their Home Organizations as authentication providers or can fall back to social logins or other authentication means if they cannot or do not want to use their institute, university, or similar Identity Provider. The situation might get even more complicated when users hop between services or use multiple external accounts to access them. To mitigate the risks of leaving the user confused, this task will focus on continuous improvements of the AAI user-facing interfaces to improve the user experience and achieve streamlining of the user workflows. These

activities will involve developing methodologies for KPIs collection and user evaluation, user testing, as well as applying the user-centric design from the start. We expect to cooperate with Tasks 1 and 2 of WP1 as well as with WPs 3-5, especially on their deliverables that overlap with authentication and authorization. We envision this cooperation mainly in providing feedback and inputs into the design aspects of the activities executed in different tasks.

To support the goal of providing the best possible user experience, this task will explore the areas of evaluating Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure as a service not just from the end-user perspective, but also from the point of view of people representing management roles utilising AAI primarily for the second A - authorization. We would like to approach this in an Agile approach by applying Continuous Discovery meaning periodical small-incremental improvements proposed to the most critical parts of the infrastructure.

From the integration perspective, we would like to explore the activity of building an AAI-centric SDK. We envision not to directly develop a set of tools, but rather to pick and evaluate existing Software components and provide in-depth guidance on their usage with the AAI

To spread the utilisation of the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure, this Task will also focus on building the community. The primary focus will be on organising events based primarily on the inputs from Relying Party integrators, but not omitting end-users and Identity providers to discuss the AAI-relevant topics, or just discuss various integrations or share recent developments in the AAI area. Last but not least, this Task will also focus on the outreach and education spread towards AAI-related customers.

- Reviewing proposals and outcomes of other tasks of WP1 and WPs 2-4 in the area of AAI-user contact points.
- Gathering inputs for other tasks of WP1 and WPs 2-4 related (AAI-focused) through interaction with the community.
- Continuous proposing and designing improvements of the workflows including the AAI from both end-user and management person perspectives.
- Improvements in accessibility aspects of the most used components of the AAI.
- Establishing methods for evaluating AAI as a service from the end-user (researcher, RP) perspective - UX as a Service (UXaaS).
- Organising regular events for building the AAI-focused community composed of end-users, integrators, and managers.
- Explore possibilities to create an AAI SDK - a toolkit to integrate easily with the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D2.1	Reference implementation of passwordless login as an alternative authentication mechanism in Life Science AAI	FI-CSC	M12
D2.2	Blueprint document proposing Identity governance model in the AAI context	CZ-MUNI	M30
D2.3	Architecture proposal for effective de-provisioning in a distributed environment	CZ-MUNI	M36
D2.4	Design of an extension to record policy agreements defined by Relying Parties in the AAI environment	CZ-MUNI	M6
D2.5	Definition of the repetitive authorization tasks performed by RPs with a proposal for transfer into the AAI environment together with Proof of Concept demonstration	LU-UNILU	M24

D2.6	Guidelines for Relying Party integrators on designing AAI-related user interfaces	CZ-MUNI	M15
D2.7	Definition of the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the AAI as a service with a methodology for the continuous gathering of inputs for such metrics	GR-ATHENA	M27
D2.8	Summary of Training Resources registered in TeSS	CZ-MUNI	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M2.1	Analysis of the eID and digital wallets into a distributed AAI-based environment	FI-CSC	M18
M2.2	Integration scheme for commercial and non-academic subjects proposed	CZ-MUNI	M24
M2.3	Proposal for extending GA4GH Passports into finer-granularity level authorization (file in dataset and/or contents of file levels)	LU-UNILU	M15
M2.4	Evaluation of the AAI API gateway concept performed	CZ-MUNI	M36
M2.5	Establishment of periodical community-centred engagement calls	CZ-MUNI	M3
M2.6	End-user-centred evaluation of AAI user interfaces collected via a questionnaire or similar method with proposals for improvements	GR-ATHENA	M9

Work Package 3 - Protected access to sensitive data for analysis

WP 3	Lead Partner: DE-BIH/Charite, FI-CSC	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
DE-BIH - Sven Twardziok (lead)		
FI-CSC - Stefan Negru (lead)		
CZ-MUNI - Adam Skrášek (member)		
CZ-CESNET - Pavel Vyskočil (member)		
CZ-MUNI - Matej Antol (member)		
LU- LNDS G.I.E. - Christophe Trefois (member)		
LU-UNILU - Venkata Satagopam (member)		
LU-UNILU - Soumyabrata Ghosh (member)		
DE-BIH - Ulrike Taron (member)		
DE-FZJ - Alexander Sczyrba (member)		
DE-FZJ - Nils Hoffmann (member)		
CH-SIB - Alexander Kanitz (member)		
DE-DKFZ - Luiz Gadelha (member)		
GR-AUTH Christos Ouzounis (member)		
FR-INRAE - Franck Giacomoni (member)		
BE-VIB - Frederik Coppens (member)		
BE-VIB - Dilza Campos (member)		
IT-INFN/CNR - Giacinto Donvito (member)		
IT-INFN/CNR - Marco Tangaro (member)		
WP Key External Collaborations		
AU-AUS Biocommons - Steven Manos (member)		
Abbreviations		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TEE - Trusted Execution Environment • TRE - Trusted Research Environment • SDE - Sensitive/Secure Data Environment (ref) • SPE - Sensitive/Secure Processing Environment (ref) 		

Objectives

Sensitive data is a critical asset for the ability to carry out essential research in even potentially critical situations, e.g. as proven during the COVID-19 pandemic. Providing easy access to such data speeds up the research process, resulting in faster development of new disease cures, or exploring and further understanding of rare diseases. However, by nature, input data for such research tasks contain sensitive information and thus needs to be correctly handled and protected. In the previous ELIXIR programme, the Compute Platform has been working in this area already, and we would like to continue this effort.

We expect to deliver to researchers a framework of products for secure access to sensitive data for use in a wide range of research settings. Our aim is to build a complex solution covering the process from the start (data discovery) through the analysis/processing up to the very end (research publication finalisation). It involves building and evolving a framework of tools for the secure discovery of sensitive data, enabling research groups to then implement and adapt to their needs using standard components in the framework. Moving further in the process, tools for possible access negotiation, secure transfer of the data to a computing environment, executing the computing workflow, and last but not least, delivery or interpretation of the result in a secure way must be considered. The work will be supported by new external funding in the Horizon Europe INFRA-EOSC and INFRA-DEV Programmes as well as the ongoing development in the GDI project.

The whole process needs to be accompanied by also focusing on Authentication, Authorization, Auditing, and optional accounting, and aiming to be in coherence with the regulations in a transnational, federated environment. Hereby we will closely align the activities of WP₃ with WP₂, WP₄ and WP₅. We will identify, build and gather technical solutions on top of the outcomes of previously carried out work in the ELIXIR programme, such as leveraging on and further development of the AAI and cloud infrastructures, sensitive data management platforms (REMS), federated EGA repositories, and similar. In order to understand how such environments can be utilised by researchers the aim is to provide guidance documentation on both the technical and organisational measures to secure the data as well as outreach to researchers through workshops in order to get feedback on how such services can be utilised.

Description of Work

Activity 1 Sensitive data access as a process (leads: *Sven Twardziok (DE), Stefan Negru (FI)*, members: *Adam Skrášek (CZ), Sven Twardziok (DE), Ulrike Taron (DE), Nils Hoffmann (DE), Alexander Kanitz (CH), Stefan Negru (FI), Frederik Coppens (BE), Dilza Campos (BE), Giacinto Donvito (IT), Marco Tangaro (IT), Luiz Gadelha (DE), Kaur Alasoo (EE)*, key external collaborations: *Steven Manos (AU)*)

Researchers may require access to sensitive data in different scenarios, which we here describe as use cases. The aim of this task is to collect and document potential use cases for accessing sensitive data in detail. These use cases will be refined, revised and extended over the course of the project. Currently, the different use cases include:

- **Direct access to data in a repository:** Here, data is archived in a single database. Either directly by the user or indirectly via a platform, the user requests access to the data. The user is then authorised to use a specific set of data. To do this, the user logs on to a database or platform and transfers the data in encrypted form to their own secure environment. In the secure environment, the user can decrypt the data and analyse it further. For example, a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) or can be used here by the user.
- **Federated database:** The data of interest is stored in a federated form on different data nodes. The data nodes provide metadata via APIs, which can be browsed in a central portal. Through the central portal, a user can request access to selected data at the respective data nodes. The nodes then grant the user access to individual datasets. The data is then collected from the nodes, combined and being made available to the user either for data transfer or for processing within a TRE.

- Centralised platform: The platform contains centralised sensitive data. Users can request access to a subset of the data. If authorised, users can then log into the platform and work directly with the data. This is done, for example, by running workflows or interactive analysis using scripts. The platform provides users with a secure VRE for this purpose.
- Federated processing: Here, sensitive data resides on different nodes that are not directly connected and the transfer of data to other environments is restricted. The nodes provide APIs through which analysis can be performed on the data, which together forms a secure processing environment (SPE). The user can perform an analysis that combines data from different sources (nodes) by executing an analysis on a platform, which then distributes individual tasks to different nodes based on where the data is available. The results are then combined and being made available to a user. A special case of this is federated learning, where models are trained in several iterations and updated on different data sets. Application of technologies such as Confidential Containers (<https://github.com/confidential-containers>) will also be in the scope of this use-case.

The individual use cases are then modelled as processes, defining the access as a process from the start (decision "I want to do something which includes sensitive? data") to the very end (publication of results). Access to data also includes fine grained access to sensitive data e.g. per dataset/file/or portions of a file, as part of the access. This will include not just providing access but also access revocation procedures and triggered actions. Based on these processes, we will formulate requirements on the security of the platforms, data transmission, encryption, policies, standards, and authentication and authorization infrastructures

- Define different use-cases and access scenarios (federated, centralised, hybrid, direct/indirect access, etc.)
- Formulate and write down processes for each scenario
- Provide list of requirements and preconditions for each scenario, including patient consents, GDPR implementation, national regulatory, data types, analysis types
- Infrastructure support tools + requirements (AAI, data sharing, communications, ...)
- Clarify TRE (Trusted Research Environment) vs SPE (Sensitive Processing Environment) vs SDE (Secure Data Environments) vs TEE (Trusted Execution Environment) and their suitability for each use case; gather external existing definitions

Activity 2 Sensitive Processing Environment Services (leads: Stefan Negru (FI), Sven Twardziok (DE), members: Pavel Vyskočil (CZ), Christophe Trefois (LU), Venkata Satagopam (LU), Soumyabrata Ghosh (LU), Sven Twardziok (DE), Nils Hoffmann (DE), Alexander Kanitz (CH), Dominik F. Bucik (CZ), Thanasis Vergoulis (GR), Eleni Adamidi (GR), Luiz Gadelha (DE), Stefan Negru (FI), Giacinto Donvito (IT), Marco Tangaro (IT), Kaur Alasoo (EE), Frederik Coppens (BE), Dilza Campos (BE), key external collaborations: Steven Manos (AU))

In WP3.2 we will support the technical implementation of secure platforms by, among other things, linking the use cases from WP3.1 with the framework components provided by WP2 and WP4. On the basis of a catalogue of services, we will enable the development of secure environments that meet the requirements of at least one of the use cases defined in WP3.1. These environments will combine authentication and authorisation features from WP2 with the solutions and services from WP4. For demonstration purposes, the platform will be implemented, tested and documented in cloud environments. Experiences, gaps and issues from the use case implementations will be fed back to WP2 and WP4.

- Developing and demonstrating a distributed SPE secure environment demonstrators based on the architecture outcomes of WP3.1
- Integration of the SPEs with AAI and feeding back requirements on the SPE-compliant AAI
- Integration of the SPEs with selected cloud infrastructures and feeding back requirements on the SPE-compliant cloud environment
- Layered extensible framework for operationalising individual data security solutions (e.g., different encryption, privacy, isolation methods like Crypt4GH, homomorphic encryption, differential privacy, TEEs)
- GA4GH standards, gaps and implementations in GDI and related initiatives
 - Data discovery tools + requirements (Beacon+Beacon network)

- Data transfer tools + requirements (htsget)
- Data storage tools + requirements (FEGA)
- Data access control + requirements (REMS)
- Analysis execution tools + requirements (WES+TES)
- High-level use-cases we want to enable
 - Batch / workflow-based analysis
 - Interactive data analysis
 - Federated learning
- Provide blueprints for national cloud providers environments
- Communication strategy to service providers, developers, integrators, ...
- Monitoring, auditing, provenance collection best practices (coordinate with WP4)

Activity 3 Guidance and outreach (leads: *Christophe Trefois (LU), Ulrike Taron (DE)*, members: *Christophe Trefois (LU), Sven Twardziok (DE), Nils Hoffmann (DE), Ulrike Taron (DE), Nadina Foggetti (IT), Stefan Negru (FI), Frederik Coppens (BE), Dilza Campos (BE), Brane Leskošek (SI)*)

General direction of the subpackage WP3.3 is towards landscaping and availability of documentation/policy, alignment and mutual exchange on standards, guidelines, SOPs and in practice handling of sensitive data access.

These Sensitive Data Processing environments will be implemented, tested and documented as part of WP 3.2, yet the providers of such environments need to be able to reach out with researchers how such environments are run and under what conditions they can be made use of. For these reasons WP 3.3 will seek to bring providers of SPE as well as consult with Legal and Ethics Officers in order to list:

- User policies for SPEs on working with sensitive data (out of scope is compliance with legislation and frameworks)
- Service policies
- Infrastructure policies

This will result in a guidance document on technical and organisational security measures for protection and working of sensitive data.

- At the same time during this work package we will investigate through workshops:
- Involvement of patient organisations / other stakeholder organisations / representatives as guests / participants of the workshop(s)
- Connection to national medical informatics infrastructures (e.g. NUM & MII in Germany)
- EU Cross border data sharing or International (US, Asia) working with /sharing sensitive data

Plan of work will include:

- Organising Workshops
 - Cross-initiative workshop - in order to get feedback into the work ongoing into WP3 we aim to have the first workshop at the end of the first year of the programme - e.g. GDI cross leverage
 - BYO(S)D - Bring-your-own-synthetic-data Workshop(s)
- Developing training material
 - Involve Nodes which can train researchers on their SPE with synthetic data or even organise training sessions

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D3.1	Documentation of use-cases and processes	DE-BIH	M18

D3.2	Documentation of technical requirements on platforms, data handling and AAI infrastructure	FI-CSC	M18
D3.3	Publication about detailed challenges and solutions for selected use-cases for sensitive processing environments	DE-BIH	M36
D3.4	Develop training materials for Sensitive Data Environment Services and optionally hold trainings on set material (online or in person)	DE-BIH	M24
D3.5	Guidance document on technical and organisational security measures for protection and working of sensitive data (DPO, data anonymization, data transport, access, storage and compute and any additional security measures)	FI-CSC	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M3.1	Description of use-cases and access scenarios	DE-BIH	M6
M3.2	Our understanding of TREs, SPEs, SDEs and TEEs for ELIXIR users	FI-CSC	M6
M3.3	Defining the access as a process for different use-cases	DE-BIH	M12
M3.4	Perform demonstrations of solutions for selected use-cases	FI-CSC	M24
M3.5	Provide reference implementations with checklist inventory	DE-BIH	M24
M3.6	Organizing Workshops - at least 2 workshops	FI-CSC	M24

Work Package 4 - Multi Cloud Infrastructure Deployment

WP 4	Lead Partner: CZ-MUNI, CH-SIB, NL-SURF	
	Start month- End month: Mo1-M36	
WP Partnership		
CZ-MUNI - Viktória Spišáková (lead)		
CH-SIB - Alexander Kanitz (lead)		
NL-SURF - Ivar Janmaat (lead)		
CZ-MUNI - Lukáš Hejtmánek (member)		
CZ-MUNI - Radek Polášek (member)		
CZ-MUNI - Adrián Rošinec (member)		
CZ-CESNET - Klára Moravcová (member)		
CZ-CESNET - Milan Daneček (member)		
DE-FZJU - Alexander Sczyrba (member)		
DE-FZJU - Nils Hoffmann (member)		
DE-BIH- Valentin Schneider-Lunitz (member)		
DE-DKFZ - Luiz Gadelha (member)		
DE-Giessen - Sebastian Beyvers (member)		
EE-UTARTU - Kaur Alasoo (member)		
EMBL-EBI - Justin Clark-Casey (member)		
EMBL-EBI - Santiago Insua (member)		
GR-AUTH Christos Ouzounis (member)		
GR-ATHENA - Thanasis Vergoulis (member)		
GR-ATHENA - Eleni Adamidi (member)		
FR-CNRS - Christophe Blanchet (member)		
FI-CSC - Tristan Perard (member)		
FI-CSC - Alvaro Gonzalez (member)		
FI-CSC - Jemal Tahir (member)		
LU-UNILU - Venkata Satagopam (member)		
LU-UNILU - Sascha Herzinger (member)		

LU-UNILU - Soumyabrata Ghosh (member)	
WP Key External Collaborations	
AU-AUS Biocommons - Steven Manos	
<p>Objectives</p> <p>With use cases such as outscaling peak performance needs and bringing compute to where the data resides, rather than fetching the data first and computing on it on premise, data analytics in the Life Sciences is increasingly shifting towards the cloud. Previously, ELIXIR Compute addressed these developments by exploring hybrid cloud and containerization techniques and developing services based on widely adopted community standards, including Cloud APIs defined by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), for which ELIXIR Compute is leading a Driver Project.</p> <p>In the next phase, the various previous efforts will be bundled, hardened and - with the help of ELIXIR-internal Driver Projects including GDI - further matured. In particular, this task will coordinate the development of an ELIXIR-wide federated hybrid- and multicloud-ready set of packages consisting of various GA4GH-compatible backend microservices deployed across the ELIXIR Nodes, and a micro-frontend-based web portal to enable end users to operationalise the platform. Through it, users will be able to discover, fetch and execute a range of workflow types (e.g., CWL, Nextflow, Snakemake, Galaxy) on HPC clusters, native cloud clusters and commercial clouds, accessing data on commonly used storage solutions (e.g., s3). Access control management, the handling of sensitive data and compute-related provenance will be addressed together with WPs 2, 3 and 5, respectively.</p> <p>In addition to the ELIXIR::GA4GH cloud platform, the task will further coordinate the bundling of backend and frontend components into a "ELIXIR Cloud SDK", which will allow (1) systems administrators to easily deploy on premise, hybrid and multicloud solutions, and (2) service developers to quickly adopt the necessary APIs and guidelines to interoperate with the ELIXIR cloud platform. Finally, the WP will coordinate the engagement of use cases, Nodes and service developers, provide documentation, training and support mechanisms, and liaise and align with developments in relevant organisations beyond ELIXIR, such as GA4GH and EOSC.</p>	
<p>Description of Work</p> <p>Activity 1 Harden and expand ELIXIR Cloud SDK use case portfolio (<i>leads: Alex Kanitz (CH), Alvaro Gonzalez (FI), members: Alex Kanitz (CH), Valentin Schneider-Lunitz (DE), Alvaro Gonzalez (FI), Luiz Gadelha (DE), Lukas Hejtmanek (CZ), Viktoria Spisakova (CZ)</i>)</p> <p>Harden existing service components by improving resilience, scalability, and service security and by integrating work provided by other WPs with respect to access control, data security, and provenance/accounting/reproducibility (e.g., via RO-Crates)</p> <p>Expand existing use case portfolio with regard to compute federation, e.g., by providing support for different workflow engines/languages, compute backends and storage solutions, including integration with commercial/public cloud providers ("hybrid cloud") and specialised workload distribution logics</p> <p>Support use cases requiring service-to-service communication (e.g., distributed computing, federated learning, federated imputation), as well as additional use cases as requested by user base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete, refine and make existing ELIXIR Cloud SDK services production-ready • Integrate functionalities to support advanced access control (with WP2), data security (with WP3) and provenance tracking and reproducibility (with WP5) • Integrate functionalities provided by third party services, e.g., Jupyter, as required by users (try to integrate into existing service components, but may require development of new ones) 	

- Add functionalities to support distributed computing, federated learning & federated imputation and other use cases that require inter-service communication (try to integrate into existing service components, but may require development of new ones)
- Develop libraries for refined, use-case specific task and workflow distribution logics
- Develop new and refinement of existing GUI/micro-frontend client components
- Liaise with global community to develop standards for semantically describing workflow and tool inputs and outputs; develop client components to make use of them

Activity 2 Operationalise ELIXIR Cloud (leads: Viktória Spišaková (CZ) , Kaur Alasoo(EE) , members: Nils Hoffmann (DE), Alvaro Gonzalez (FI), Valentin Schneider-Lunitz (DE), Tristan Perard (FI), Milan Danecek (CZ))

Deploy centralised and federated ELIXIR Cloud SDK service components across different ELIXIR Nodes, deploy and maintain service registry and system to automatically upgrade service instances in the network

Develop and deploy web portal and CLI entry points that operationalise the supported ELIXIR Cloud use cases to end users

- Bring service registry to maturity, deploy and register services
- Bring automated service upgrading system to maturity, deploy central service and node-specific sidecar services, and subscribe services
- Deploy and maintain Galaxy instance as the most mature workflow framework in this context, with emphasis on high-throughput, efficient, and secure processing of the sensitive data near the data resources.
- Further develop, deploy and maintain existing web portal (<https://github.com/elixir-cloud-aai/krini>) by continuously integrating ELIXIR Cloud SDK GUI components as they become available/mature
- Develop library for command-line and programmatic access to the ELIXIR Cloud and other ELIXIR Cloud SDK-powered cloud environments

Activity 3 Policies, Documentation and Outreach (leads: Ivar Janmaat (NL), Jemal Tahir (FI), members:)

Promote ELIXIR Cloud & ELIXIR Cloud SDK within ELIXIR and global community, including industry partners

Provide extensive documentation for various audiences (end users, devs and admins), including tutorials and interactive examples

- Extend the ELIXIR Cloud / ELIXIR Cloud SDK Documentation Hub with detailed documentation for
 - End users
 - Administrators and developers
- Develop demo/example materials to highlight specific use cases for the ELIXIR Cloud and make them available to users of the web portal
- Prepare and continuously update promotion materials
- Promote the ELIXIR Cloud & ELIXIR Cloud SDK with both an academic and industry audience at various relevant events and (e.g., ELIXIR & GA4GH meetings, scientific and cloud/infrastructure-specific conferences, webinars, regular ECP meetings) and with with academic and industry partners
- Liaise with compute and data centres in the ELIXIR and adjacent (e.g., GDI) communities, as well as industry partners, to join the ELIXIR Cloud or build national/regional clouds based on ELIXIR Cloud SDK components or other GA4GH Cloud implementations

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D4.1	Portfolio of service components available to support federated compute use cases with common, advanced access control	CH-SIB	M36

	mechanisms, data security protocols and provenance/accounting support		
D4.2	Portfolio of GUI/micro-frontend components available to operationalise services	FI-CSC	M36
D4.3	Standards for describing workflow and tool inputs and outputs using / complementing bio.tools and WorkflowHub	CH-SIB	M36
D4.4	End user guide and tutorials for using the ELIXIR Cloud usage via (1) the Krini web portal or another portal making use of the ELIXIR Cloud micro-frontend components and (2) the CLI	NL-SURF	M36
D4.5	Admin user guide and tutorials for onboarding compute and/or data centres with the ELIXIR Cloud or other clouds based on the ELIXIR Cloud SDK; include document with policies/requirements for integration with ELIXIR Cloud and its individual components	FI-CSC	M36
D4.6	Demo/example materials highlighting different use cases into the ELIXIR Cloud (e.g., provide test resources for federated analytics, federated learning etc.)	NL-SURF	M36
D4.7	Promotion materials: posters/1-pagers, slide deck, website/s	FI-CSC	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M4.1	Service registry listing all deployed ELIXIR Cloud SDK service instances across the different Nodes in place	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.2	Unified CLI client library	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.3	Automatic upgrading system in place	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.4	ELIXIR Cloud is available for (selected) ELIXIR users to run workflows in different languages and individual containerised tasks	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.5	ELIXIR Cloud is available for (selected) ELIXIR users to run federated learning jobs	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.6	ELIXIR Cloud is available for (selected) ELIXIR users to run workflows in different languages and individual containerised tasks	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.7	ELIXIR Cloud is available for (selected) ELIXIR users to run federated learning jobs	CZ-MUNI	M36

Work Package 5 - Sustainability, Accounting and Provenance for Federated Analytics

WP 5	Lead Partner: DE-FZJ, GR-Athena-RC, BE-VIB	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
DE-FUB- Michael R. Crusoe (lead)		
GR-Athena RC - Thanasis Vergoulis (lead)		
BE-VIB - Paul De Geest (lead)		
GR-Athena RC - Eleni Adamidi (member)		
CZ-MUNI - Matej Antol (member)		
CH-SIB - Alexander Kanitz (member)		
EMBL-EBI - Rob Finn (member)		
NL-Erasmus Medical Center - Helena Rasche (member)		
NL-Health-RI - Anne van der Kant (member)		
UK-UniMan - Stian Soiland Reyes (member)		
DE-DKFZ - Luiz Gadelha (member)		
DE-FZJ - Nils Hoffmann (member)		
LU-UNILU - Venkata Satagopam (member)		
LU-UNILU - Soumyabrata Ghosh (member)		
BE-VIB - Rafael Andrade Buono (member)		
ELIXIR-Hub - Erika Balsyte and Despoina Sousoni (member)		
<p>Objectives</p> <p>To address the increasing complexity of life science analytics, bioinformaticians need access to advanced and large scale compute capacities, often in an international context. They need to be able to do so using sustainable compute resources which follow appropriate regulatory compliance, accounting, and provenance. While aspects of this have and are being addressed by the e-infrastructures in Europe, life scientists have additional demands for computing sensitive data which only increases the importance of appropriate audit trails which will fit with the relevant information governance and security requirements.</p> <p>In this Task ELIXIR will identify best practices in our communities, Nodes and projects in the reporting of resources (facilities, services) used to lay the groundwork for billing or other financial accounting of services (within or between institutions, and eventually across borders). The Platform will identify automated, lightweight solutions which are FAIR in practice in order to track provenance. In turn this will improve the reproducibility of scientific analysis and the recognition of relevant service providers as well as researchers</p>		

at the individual and organisational level. The Compute Platform is directly involved in relevant technical developments in secure and distributed computing in the Nodes and can help address the integration of non automated systems such as electronic notebooks.

Description of Work

Activity 1 Dashboard of ELIXIR Computing Providers (leads: Soumyabrata Ghosh (LU), Nils Hoffmann (DE), members: Alexander Kanitz (CH), Nils Hoffmann (DE), Erika Balsyte and Despoina Sousoni(Hub), Thanasis Vergoulis (GR),)

Centralised place to publish data around what compute resources are available across ELIXIR; along with compute resource reporting summaries. Output will be in both machine-readable and human-friendly forms (i.e. visualisations that can be understood by non-specialists).

To be a living (continuously updated) successor to the one-off snapshots from EOSC-Life WP7 “Cloud Observatory Report”, [ELIXIR EXCELERATE - D4.3](#), CONVERGE.

Link to WP3.1 ELIXIR Cloud Service Registry, based on [GA4GH Service Registry API](#). Implementation [under development](#), currently [deployed at the CH Node](#). There is also a [matching GUI client](#) under development, implemented as a reusable Web Component. Both could be used to power (part of) a dashboard. May also include a “living map” of ELIXIR compute.

- Gathering metadata requirements for computing resources
- Work openly with stakeholders to select already available (community) information standards to meet the identified requirements.
- Prototype receiving data from WP4.3 participants

Activity 2 Provenance consumption and production by infrastructure (leads: Michael R. Crusoe (DE), Paul de Geest (BE), members: Rafael Andrade Buono (BE), Thanasis Vergoulis (GR), Eleni Adamidi (GR), Alexander Kanitz (CH), Rob Finn (EBI), Stian Soiland-Reyes (UK), Luiz Gadelha (DE))

It is important for platforms executing computational research experiments to utilise RO-Crates aiming for reproducibility and reusability. Using this packaging format can allow bundling together all the components and dependencies of a research experiment, ensuring that it can be reproduced, re-executed, and reused in the future.

More specifically, reusability can be enhanced with the use of WorkflowRun profile RO-Crates that capture and encapsulate the entire research experiment, including data, code, parameters, and workflows. This enables that the experiment can be accurately reused, allowing other researchers to validate and build upon the results. Moreover, by packaging all the necessary components, including data sources, software versions, and configurations, RO-Crates preserve the context in which the experiment was conducted. This enhances transparency and enables others to understand the experimental setup and potentially identify any issues or improvements.

Additionally the use of RO-Crates can facilitate collaboration and sharing of research experiments. They provide a standardised format that can be easily shared among researchers, enabling them to reproduce, validate, and build upon each other's work. This promotes open science practices and fosters scientific advancements.

Use cases will come from MGnify; WP5.1; and the ELIXIR Communities.

Outcomes could include software libraries; documented cookbooks; examples web services for direct downloads with RO-Crates.

- Gathering relevant use cases
- Prototyping of a solution for provenance consumption and production
- Implementors workshop for the prototype
- Write a guidance report on final outcomes of the work

Activity 3 Reporting of resource usage (accounting) (leads: Thanasis Vergoulis (GR), Matej Antol (CZ), members: Eleni Adamidi (GR), Helena Rasche (NL), Erika Balsyte and Despoina Sousoni (Hub), Matej Antol (CZ), Martin Kuba (CZ), Anne van der Kant (NL))

Systems that provide compute resources to researchers need to implement mechanisms for tracking the resource usage of each researcher and enforcing limits to that usage. In addition, the usage data kept (including consumed resources, user numbers, geolocation, or carbon footprint) can be a valuable resource to steer user behaviour towards greening, and needs to be reported to funders and inform long-term policy-making. At the same time, they can also be useful when they are shared with the research community at large and the society for transparency. This work package will investigate the needs of the ELIXIR communities, Nodes, and projects regarding resource tracking and accounting/reporting and will explore existing mechanisms that have been implemented in various ELIXIR Nodes. Moreover, the work package will collect (where possible) feedback on the related challenges and expectations of the relevant stakeholders. Finally, the WP will develop a reference framework that can provide a standardised method for monitoring and reporting resource usage in research compute systems.

Participation in EOSC accounting topics is also envisioned as part of this WP.

- Gathering use cases on provenance consumption and production
- Prototype to be developed for reporting of resource usage
- Send out for community feedback based on prototype developed
- Workshop to carry out necessary stakeholder engagement and community alignment

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D5.1	A computing resource dashboard and related documentation	LU-UNILU	M36
D5.2	Guidance report on provenance consumption and production by infra	DE-FUB	M36
D5.3	A report detailing the requirements gathered from ELIXIR communities, Nodes, and projects regarding resource tracking and accounting	GR-ATHENA	M36
D5.4	A framework for monitoring and reporting resource usage in research compute systems	GR-ATHENA	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M5.1	A report detailing the metadata requirements for computing resources	LU-UNILU	M24
M5.2	A community proposal of a metadata model for computing resources	DE-FUB	M24
M5.3	Demonstration on provenance consumption and production by infra	BE-VIB	M24
M5.4	Workshop for WP5.2	DE-FUB	M24
M5.5	Summary of stakeholder consultations, including feedback and insights on challenges and expectations related to resource usage reporting	GR-ATHENA	M24

Table of Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverable / Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D1.1	Annual Report 2023	CZ-MUNI	Mo6
D1.2	Annual Report 2024	DE-BIH	M18
D1.3	Annual Report 2025	FI-CSC	M30
D1.4	2 Compute Platform articles submitted	CZ-MUNI	M30
D1.5	Alignment to prospective ELIXIR Cross Platform dissemination articles	DE-BIH	M30
D1.6	Preparation, writing and delivery of 2027-2028 Platform Plan	FI-CSC	M30
D1.7	End Report	CZ-MUNI	M36
M1.1	Platform F2F Event - Year 1	CZ-MUNI	M12
M1.2	Platform F2F Event - Year 2	DE-BIH	M24
M1.3	Platform F2F Event - Year 3	FI-CSC	M36
D2.1	Reference implementation of passwordless login as an alternative authentication mechanism in Life Science AAI	FI-CSC	M12
D2.2	Blueprint document proposing Identity governance model in the AAI context	CZ-MUNI	M30
D2.3	Architecture proposal for effective de-provisioning in a distributed environment	CZ-MUNI	M36
D2.4	Design of an extension to record policy agreements defined by Relying Parties in the AAI environment	CZ-MUNI	M6
D2.5	Definition of the repetitive authorization tasks performed by RPs with a proposal for transfer into the AAI environment together with Proof of Concept demonstration	LU-UNILU	M24
D2.6	Guidelines for Relying Party integrators on designing AAI-related user interfaces	CZ-MUNI	M15
D2.7	Definition of the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the AAI as a service with a methodology for the continuous gathering of inputs for such metrics	GR-ATHENA	M27
D2.8	Summary of Training Resources registered in TeSS	CZ-MUNI	M36
M2.1	Analysis of the eID and digital wallets into a distributed AAI-based environment	FI-CSC	M18

M2.2	Integration scheme for commercial and non-academic subjects proposed	CZ-MUNI	M24
M2.3	Proposal for extending GA4GH Passports into finer-granularity level authorization (file in dataset and/or contents of file levels)	LU-UNILU	M15
M2.4	Evaluation of the AAI API gateway concept performed	CZ-MUNI	M36
M2.5	Establishment of periodical community-centred engagement calls	CZ-MUNI	M3
M2.6	End-user-centred evaluation of AAI user interfaces collected via a questionnaire or similar method with proposals for improvements	GR-ATHENA	M9
D3.1	Documentation of use-cases and processes	DE-BIH	M18
D3.2	Documentation of technical requirements on platforms, data handling and AAI infrastructure	FI-CSC	M18
D3.3	Publication about detailed challenges and solutions for selected use-cases for sensitive processing environments	DE-BIH	M36
D3.4	Develop training materials of Sensitive Data Environment Services and optional hold trainings on set material (online or in person)	DE-BIH	M24
D3.5	Guidance document on technical and organisational security measures for protection and working of sensitive data (DPO, data anonymization, data transport, access, storage and compute and any additional security measures)	FI-CSC	M36
M3.1	Description of use-cases and access scenarios	DE-BIH	M6
M3.2	Our understanding of TREs, SPEs, SDEs and TEEs for ELIXIR users	FI-CSC	M6
M3.3	Defining the access as a process for different use-cases	DE-BIH	M12
M3.4	Perform demonstrations of solutions for selected use-cases	FI-CSC	M24
M3.5	Provide reference implementations with checklist inventory	DE-BIH	M24
M3.6	Organizing Workshops - at least 2 workshops	FI-CSC	M24
D4.1	Portfolio of services to support federated compute use cases with common, advanced access control mechanisms, data security protocols and provenance/accounting support	CH-SIB	M36
D4.2	Portfolio of GUI/micro-frontend components to operationalise services	FI-CSC	M36
D4.3	Standards for describing workflow and tool inputs and outputs using / complementing bio.tools and WorkflowHub	CH-SIB	M36

D4.4	End user guide and tutorials for using the ELIXIR Cloud usage via (1) the Krini web portal or another portal making use of the ELIXIR Cloud micro-frontend components and (2) the CLI	NL-SURF	M36
D4.5	Admin user guide and tutorials for onboarding compute and/or data centres with the ELIXIR Cloud or other clouds based on the ELIXIR Cloud SDK; include document with policies/requirements for integration with ELIXIR Cloud and its individual components	FI-CSC	M36
D4.6	Demo/example materials highlighting different use cases into the ELIXIR Cloud (e.g., provide test resources for federated analytics, federated learning etc.)	NL-SURF	M36
D4.7	Promotion materials: posters/1-pagers, slide deck, website/s	FI-CSC	M36
M4.1	Service registry listing all deployed ELIXIR Cloud SDK service instances across the different Nodes in place	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.2	Unified CLI client library	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.3	Automatic upgrading system in place	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.4	ELIXIR Cloud is available for (selected) ELIXIR users to run workflows in different languages and individual containerised tasks	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.5	ELIXIR Cloud is available for (selected) ELIXIR users to run federated learning jobs	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.6	ELIXIR Cloud is available for (selected) ELIXIR users to run workflows in different languages and individual containerised tasks	CZ-MUNI	M36
M4.7	ELIXIR Cloud is available for (selected) ELIXIR users to run federated learning jobs	CZ-MUNI	M36
D5.1	A computing resource dashboard and related documentation	LU-UNILU	M36
D5.2	Guidance report on provenance consumption and production by infra	DE-FUB	M36
D5.3	A report detailing the requirements gathered from ELIXIR communities, Nodes, and projects regarding resource tracking and accounting	GR-ATHENA	M36
D5.4	A framework for monitoring and reporting resource usage in research compute systems	GR-ATHENA	M36
M5.1	A report detailing the metadata requirements for computing resources	LU-UNILU	M24
M5.2	A community proposal of a metadata model for computing resources	DE-FUB	M24

M5.3	Demonstration on provenance consumption and production by infra	BE-VIB	M24
M5.4	Workshop for WP5.2	DE-FUB	M24
M5.5	Summary of stakeholder consultations, including feedback and insights on challenges and expectations related to resource usage reporting	GR-ATHENA	M24

Appendix A: Partner information

Appendix A: Partner contact information

Institution	Contact Name
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